

Construction and Validation of STEM-EF model

Phase 1: Building Thematic Network

Stage	Description
1	Identify themes and codes about emotional factors in thematic network
2	Support with emotional aspects in Scrum in Emotional Scrum aspects
3	Support with agile aspects in Agile Support

Phase 2: Building STEM-EF instrument

Stage	Description
1	Building the question (items) in STEM-EF in STEM-EF building 1 , STEM-EF building 2 , STEM-EF building 3 , STEM-EF building 4 and STEM-EF building 5
2	And the page Iteration 1 - Responses are the responses from the first content assessment and TAM assessment with the 11 Scrum experts from the following survey applied first-survey-with-scrum-specialists .
3	And the page IVC - Iteration 1 the CVI _r were calculated considering the 11 specialists.
4	And the page Initial Focus Group Questions The questions reformulated at the end of the first evaluation are presented, which were analyzed based on a focus group and interviews with 3 Scrum experts.
5	And the page Review of Questions - Focus Group Analysis the analyses carried out in the focus group and the final questions of this phase are shown.
6	And the page Final Focus Group Questions the initial and final questions of the focus group are presented.
7	And the page Analysis of the 2nd Iteration the responses from the second iteration are presented.
8	And the page Focus Group + Assessments 2 and 3 the integrated analyses of the focus group and iterations 2 and 3 are presented
9	And the page TRANSLATION- Analysis 3 iteration the translations carried out are presented.

10	And the page Iteration 2 - Responses all responses from Iteration 2 obtained from the survey responses are presented second-survey-with-scrum-specialists .
11	And the page I2 - Calculation - IVC-TAM the CVI calculations and TAM evaluations of the first and second iterations are presented.
12	And the page Questions by factors the questions are presented separated by factors.
13	And the page Iteration 3 - Responses all responses from the third iteration of the survey are presented third-survey-with-scrum-team-members .
14	And the page I3 - Calculation - IVC-TAM all CVI calculations and TAM evaluation for iterations 1, 2 and 3 are presented.

Phase 3: Research used to validate STEM-EF

<p>Firstly, Scrum experts were consulted to verify the validity of the content of the proposed instrument as per the link below.</p> <p>first-survey-with-scrum-specialists</p>
<p>Second validation of the items of the proposed instrument</p> <p>second-survey-with-scrum-specialists</p>
<p>Third validation of the items of the proposed instrument</p> <p>third-survey-with-scrum-team-members</p>